

PIOTR Z. BIAŁOOKI

**On identity of *Otiorhynchus laevipennis* STIERLIN,
1888 and *Otiorhynchus biroi* CSIKI, 1943 (Coleoptera:
Curculionidae, Entiminae, Otiorhynchini), with a new
synonymy**

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State Plant Health and Seed Inspectorate, ul. Na Stoku 48, 80-874 Gdańsk, Poland,

e-mail: pbialooki@poczta.onet.pl

Abstract: *Otiorhynchus laevipennis* STIERLIN, 1888 now placed in the subgenus *Rimenostolus* REITTER, 1912 actually belongs to the subgenus *Melasennus* REITTER, 1912 (**new subgeneric placement**). It is sometimes confused with *Otiorhynchus biroi* CSIKI, 1943 from the subgenus *Misenatus* REITTER, 1912. Some comments concerning their determination are provided. Lectotype of *O. laevipennis* is designated. The recently described (in the subgenus *Misenatus*) *Otiorhynchus johanna*e COLONNELLI, 2018 is a synonym of *Otiorhynchus laevipennis* STIERLIN, 1888 (**new synonymy**).

Key words: *Otiorhynchus*, synonymy, systematics, Greece.

INTRODUCTION

The Palearctic Entiminae tribe Otiorhynchini (type species *Otiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1822) since the very beginning (GERMAR 1822) has been practically identified with the genus *Otiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1826. Only relatively recently the systematic structure of the tribe received some attention (MAGNANO, 1998) but nevertheless the present situation concerning both genus- and species-level can be only defined as chaos. MAGNANO (1998) splitted off some groups from *Otiorhynchus* and raised them to distinct genera and also erected several new (sub)genera but resulting classification was abandoned even by its author (MAGNANO & ALONSO-ZARAZAGA 2013 and ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). As a result, the present classification of the tribe based on more than one hundred never satisfactorily described and totally non-hierarchized (sub)genera i.e. on only somewhat modified classification proposed by REITTER (1912, 1912a, 1913, 1914) is still a source of many misunderstandings. The present note deals with some of them.

Acronyms. **BIAL** – Piotr Z. Białooki, Sopot, Poland; **HNHM** – Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum Budapest, Hungary (Hungarian Natural History Museum); **SDEI** – Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg, Germany; **WANA** – Marek Wanat, University of Wrocław, Poland.

RESULTS

Subfamily Entiminae

Tribe Otiiorhynchini

Genus *Otiiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1822 (type species *Otiiorhynchus rhacusensis* GERMAR, 1822)

Subgenus *Melasesmnus* REITTER, 1912 (type species *Otiiorhynchus ovalipennis* BOHEMAN, 1842)

Otiiorhynchus laevipennis STIERLIN, 1888

= *Otiiorhynchus (Misenatus) johannae* COLONNELLI, 2018 (**syn. n.**)

Material examined: lectotype male [hereby designated], dissected: Creta; Viano/ v. Oertzen./ coll. Stierlin/ Syntypus [red, printed]/ *O. laevipennis* m./ Dtsch. Ent. Inst.; Eberswalde [SDEI] 25.05.2017 Greece, Crete, E Psiloritis Mts., above Lakos Migerou refuge 1900 m, leg. P. Białooki\ same but 1650 m, leg. P. Białooki and M. Wanat\ 28.05.2017 Greece, Crete, Dikti Mts. rd from Avrakontes 1200m, leg. M. Wanat and P. Białooki, 37 exx. [BIAL; WANA] 19.05.2018 Greece, Crete, Avrakontes (Lasithiou), leg. P. Białooki, 59 exx. [BIAL].

Otiiorhynchus laevipennis has always been little known species. STIERLIN (1888) placed it in the subgenus *Tournieria* (i.e. *Tournieria* sensu lato) and within it in the *anadolicus*-group. REITTER (1914) placed *O. laevipennis* in the subgenus *Rimenostolus* REITTER, 1912 (type species *Otiiorhynchus globicollis* HOCHHUT, 1847). The same placement was proposed in the two recently published catalogues of palaearctic weevils (MAGNANO & ALONSO-ZARAZAGA 2013 and ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2017). [MAGNANO (1998 and 2013) confused *Dibredus* and *Rimenostolus* and erroneously synonymized these two groups]. Actually *O. laevipennis* is very similar to *O. ovalipennis* and close relationship of both species is beyond all doubts. I examined one of a series of three syntypes (as stated in original description) of *O. laevipennis*; it matches original description in all details (both labels and specimen), so in order to fix the name I hereby designate lectotype [*Otiiorhynchus laevipennis* STIERLIN, 1888; lectotype; des. P. Białooki 2008]. *O. laevipennis* differs from *O. ovalipennis*, except for disparate sculpture of elytra, smooth and matt in the former and subtuberculate and shiny in the latter, only in several subtle characters, mainly in on average smaller body, shorter rostrum, more robust antennal scape and elytral vestiture less developed. Recently published *Otiiorhynchus johannae* COLONNELLI, 2018 is a synonym of *O. laevipennis*, species described by Stierlin from Crete and locally common from low mountain localities, where it is collected by beating various trees and shrubs during the night, to high alpine steppes, where it is occasionally found under stones. Since the description of *O. johannae* is quite satisfactory (including photographs of habitus and aedeagus) here only some comments concerning systematic position of the species discussed. The reason for which Colonnelli placed *O. johannae* in *Misenatus* is unclear since the author provided no explanation in the original description. True systematic position of this species can be easily established based on general structure of aedeagus. Such narrow, strongly elongate pedon is very typical of *Tournieria* sensu lato

(among others *Rimenostolus* and *Dibredus*) and altogether unknown in *Dorymerus* sensu lato (to which belongs also *Misenatus*). Another differences between *Tournieria* sensu lato and *Dorymerus* sensu lato (roughly identical with sections 3 and 2 respectively in MAGNANO 1998) consist in distal margin of fore femur tooth uneven in *Tournieria* and straight in *Dorymerus* (this character is obscured in *O. laevipennis* due to strong reduction of the tooth), different structure of the connection of prothorax and elytra, and elongate rostrum in *Dorymerus* while at most isodiametric in *Tournieria* (REITTER 1912).

***Otiorhynchus biroi* CSIKI, 1943**

Material examined: 9 syntypes, each with labels: Creta Biro/ Mt. Ida 2200 m/ Coll. E. Csiki/ Holotypus [or Paratypus] *Otiorhynchus Biroi* 1942. [museal labels with orange frame], some of them additionally with: Antr. Iovis Mt. Ida [HNHM] 25-26.05.2017 Greece, Crete, E Psiloritis Mts., above Lakos Migerou refuge 1900 m, leg. P. Białooki, 67 exx. [BIAL; WANA].

Otiorhynchus biroi belongs to the subgenus *Misenatus*; it shows all diagnostic characters of this group, structure of aedeagus similar to other *Misenatus*-species in particular. I studied syntypes housed in Hungarian Natural History Museum in Budapest; all represent species described by Csiki and are identical with recently collected materials from locus typicus, so designation of lectotype is unnecessary. Voss 1948 depicted aedeagus of *Otiorhynchus trojanus* collected on Crete (on locus typicus) but most probably he confused this species with *O. biroi*. I have never collected *O. trojanus* on Crete and I have not seen any material from this island. *O. biroi*, which is endemic to Crete, is very similar to *O. trojanus* (depicted in COLONNELLI 2018), and differs from that species known from continental Greece and westernmost Asia Minor (this record decidedly needs confirmation) mainly in details of aedeagus but it can be instantly identified by smooth shiny elytra with minute stria punctures. *O. biroi* is occasionally confused also with *O. laevipennis*. All remarks concerning *Dorymerus* sensu lato and *Tournieria* sensu lato are applicable in this case since this pair of species also represent these two different major groups within Otiorhynchini.

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